

Community behavioural changes towards handwashing device using and maintenances in Rohingya Refugee camps

Problem statement:

Diarrheal disease may happen for different kinds of reason and it has common cause for morbidity and mortality. Rohingya refugees are the most vulnerable community due to living in overcrowded place and limited access to basic needs. Here public health risk is high. NGOs and INGOs run water, sanitation and hygiene projects under different donors in order to reduce the public health risk. Hand washing device installation and its repair and maintenance is a common activity in Rohingya camp level. Community awareness program and different kinds of community engagement approach like RANAS, PHAST, CHAST integrated with this activity. The main target is to community behavioural changes towards handwashing device maintenance and using. Handwashing device installed besides latrines with ensuring soap. It aims to remove pathogens from hand after defecating in the toilet. Though the improvement has happened since 2017 influx, but the expected improvement has not found in the present post emergency period. Because handwashing device often time stealing, broken the tap that attached with drum, water drum stealing and misusing and conflict among community members to keep the water availability in the drum. As a result, the use of hand washing device has not seen improved drastically.

Initiative of the handwashing device installation and community engagement:

As per SPHERE guideline, “Soap and water at a handwashing station (one station per shared toilet or one per household).” Three Area Focal Agencies are UNHCR, IOM and unicef are playing vital role to implement the WASH activities through partnership approach in 34 camps. According to UNHCR situation report in December 2020, [UNHCR continues to support preventative sanitation works and hygiene promotion in refugee camps. Since the beginning of the response, 96,428 handwashing tippy taps have been installed in refugee camps at a household level. 14,928 hand washing devices at latrine blocks and 307 hand washing devices at public places have been set up. All refugee households have been provided with bath and laundry soap through several distribution cycles; through UNHCR’s partner, over 60,000 households received soap in December alone]¹. According to unicef situation report in March 2021, [An estimated 166,098 individuals (47 per cent female including 1 per cent PWD) were reached through the installation of 8,029 low-cost handwashing devices in households, 30 handwashing devices at public places]². According to ISCG situation report in June 2021, [41,020 new handwashing facilities were installed in June (37,311 in households, 3,608 near latrine blocks and 106 in public spaces)]³. Community consultation has made for designing the hand washing device so that community could use comfortably. [OXFAM installed a prototype of the handwashing station and then interviewed about 43 people after Rohingya community used it. Later Oxfam changed the handwashing device design based on the community consultation]⁴. Hand washing device using, and maintenance is a key part of hygiene promotion. There is certain latrine user groups and community

leader to take care of the handwashing devices. The follow up meeting also held with latrine user groups and community leader for preventing the tap of the drum stealing, hand washing device stealing, water drum stealing and to ensure the water availability in the drum. RANAS is a behavioral change approach that is implementing in the camps by different implementing agencies. Community Maintenance Team (CMT) approach is implementing for the repair and maintenance of the handwashing devices that is a completely voluntary approach. Despite having all the efforts, still most of the hand washing devices are non-functional in the Rohingya refugees camps.

Identified reasons to failure to change the community behavior changes toward handwashing devices using and maintenance at optimum level:

- ▶ Community yet not feel ownership to take care of hand washing devices.
- ▶ Few community members stolen the handwashing devices for earning money.
- ▶ Children often time breaking the drum taps.
- ▶ Sometimes water availability sufficiently not found at nearest water point in order to keep water availability in the drum.
- ▶ The conflict exists among community members for the responsibility of water keeping in the drum.
- ▶ Demonstration activities are not performing well with targeting hand washing device using and maintenances.

The way forward to mitigate the challenges:

Community ownership create is not easy task in the context of refugee context. But at least the minimum responsibilities may grow up into them through sensitizing community consensus, consciousness, and close collaboration as back up support hand. The question may arise the sensitizing process is continuously performing but why this thing repeatedly saying. The reason is that the applied behaviours change technique approach needs to be review for the effective sensitization. Community action plan and routine monitoring as well as process documentation needs to emphasize to preventing the hand washing device stealing, tap stealing, drum stealing and reducing the conflict issues. Demonstration activities is more effective for in depth realization. Community always prefer to street drama, demonstration activities than lecture-based session. Because they do not feel bore in demonstration activities session. In comparison with host communities, Rohingya community have plenty time to spend into educative session. This is a scope to rethink by implementing agencies how this opportunity can be utilized for getting effective outcome on community engagement.

Conclusion:

The above discussion made only on handwashing devices functionality that is providing with shared latrine. Rohingya emergency program already passed near about four years.

Now the post emergency period is on going. But still to keep the hand washing device functionality is a massive challenge. Because stealing and damage cannot be prevented with applying community sensitization activities. As a responsible person of WASH camp focal, the gaps have been caught in my eyes. The gaps have drawn here with way forward to mitigation steps.

References:

In the section title "Initiative of the handwashing device installation and community engagement", the four references have taken from different web sites that hyperlink created with each number of references in that section.

About the Author:

The author name is Md. Ziaul Hoque. He has around 11 years job experiences in the development sector. He is now working in an international NGO in Rohingya Refugee Program under the department of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH). For any query, please reach to myziaul@gmail.com.